

ESSENTIAL OIL FROM THE RESIN OF *COMMIPHORA MUKUL*, HOOK. EX. STOCKS

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The chief components of the essential oil from the resin of *Balsamodendron Mukul* are 64% myrcene, 11% dimyrcene, and some polymyrcene.

Commiphora Mukul, a small tree of the Burseraceae family, is found on the rocky ground in the arid zones of Rajputana and Khandesh. An oleo-resin exudes naturally or from incisions made on the bark in the cold season. This brownish or greenish resin, with an attractive perfume, is popularly known as "Gugal" (Mahisakshi Gugal) and is used as an incense and also as a drug in the treatment of rheumatism.

R. N. Chopra ("Indigenous Drugs of India", 1933, p. 287) mentions that *Commiphora mukul* is allied to *Commiphora myrrha* which is indigenous to North-East Africa, and which contains from 2.5 to 10% of an essential oil. He mentions that although the resin from the first is not worked up like that from the second, the essential oil components of the first will be very similar to those from the second. These are cumaldehyde, eugenol, cresol, pinene and dipentene.

An essential oil from the resin of *Commiphora mukul* has been described by D. Satyanarayan Naidu (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1927, p. 104) who extracted the resin with light petrol and obtained a viscous, golden yellow liquid which on distillation under reduced pressure gave two fractions. These fractions do not appear to have been worked up, but are merely described as esters. Essential oil from the gum resin was also extracted by Dutt, Ghosh and Chopra (*Ind. J. Med. Res.*, 1942, 30, 33) who report an yield of 1.45% of the essential oil.

With a view to studying the chemistry of the volatile components of this medicinally important resin, and further to ascertaining whether the medicinal properties are on account of the volatile or the non-volatile part of the resin, the author undertook the present work. As will be seen from what follows our observations do not agree with those recorded or suggested by the authors referred to above.

The fresh resin was collected under the personal supervision of the author from the arid zones around Jaisalmer in Rajputana in September last year, and it was definitely ascertained that the product we were dealing with was from the plant *Commiphora mukul*.

On steam-distillation, the resin affords a yellowish white oil in 0.37% yield with fragrant smell resembling that from unripe mangoes. It has the following physical and chemical constants. Those of the oil from *Commiphora myrrha* are also shown alongside for comparison.

TABLE I

<i>C. Mukul.</i>	<i>C. Myrrah.</i>
d_{20}^{20} , 0.8278	d_{15}^{15} , 0.988-1.024*
n_D^{20} , 1.4800	n_D^{20} , 1.5196-1.5274*
$[\alpha]_D^{20}$, 0°	$[\alpha]_D$, 29-93*
Sapon. value, 50	Sapon. value, 16-40*

*Gildemeister and Hoffmann, 3rd Ed., Vol. III, p. 152.

Fractionation of the oil gave two fractions with fairly constant boiling points. Fraction (I), constituting about 64% of the oil, seemed to be a single compound, as on repeated distillation it boiled within the narrow range of 168°-170°. Its preliminary quantitative analysis showed that it was a hydrocarbon mixed with a small amount of some oxygen-containing compound. This was removed by distillation over sodium. The pure compound, so obtained, gave on analysis results agreeing with the formula $C_{10}H_{16}$ of a terpene. This absorbed bromine but did not give a solid bromine addition compound. Nor did it give a solid derivative such as a nitrosite or a nitrosochloride. An additional difficulty about the terpene was that it could not be kept long without polymerisation. The polymerised product distilled at the temperature of fraction (II) described later, and from comparison of the properties it appeared that fraction (I) polymerised to fraction (II).

The high degree of unsaturation of the compound suggested that it was probably an open-chain terpene. This inference has been proved to be correct from its molecular refraction [found: M. R., 46.85; M. R. for $(C_{10}H_{16})_2$, 46.66] and by the fact that it combined with maleic anhydride by the process of Diels and Alder (*Annalen*, 1929, 470, 81) and gave an adduct melting at 33-34°. On hydrolysis, the adduct gave a dicarboxylic acid with a wide melting range of 106° to 114°. By repeated crystallisation from ethyl acetate, the melting range could be narrowed to 110°-114°, but the homogeneity of the crystalline form and the purity of the acid still remain uncertain.

The acid, however, forms a characteristic, sparingly soluble, crystalline acid potassium salt. By decomposing this salt with an acid the dicarboxylic acid melting at 112-14° was obtained. From the m.p. of the adduct of maleic anhydride with the terpene, and that of the dicarboxylic acid by hydrolysis of the latter, as also from the analysis of the corresponding acid potassium salt, the terpene seems to be myrcene (I) and the adduct is 4-isohexenyltetrahydrophthalic anhydride (II).

A comparison between the properties of myrcene and its derivatives with those of our compound and its derivatives is made in Table II.

TABLE II

Properties.	The compound.	Myrcene.	References.
B.p.	106°-109°/120 mm. or 168°-170°/750 mm.	51°-53°/10 mm.	(Farmer & Sutton, <i>J Chem Soc.</i> , 1941, 145). (Semler, <i>Ber.</i> , 1901, 34, 3126)
Density	0.8070 at 30°	0.8028 at 15.8°	(Rijkman, <i>Chem. Zentr.</i> , 1937, II, 1211)
n_D	1.4680 at 31°	1.4722 at 20°	(Rijkman, <i>loc. cit.</i>).
M.R.	45.85	$C_{10}H_{16}$ 3, 46.66	
M.p. of the maleic anhydride adduct	33-34°	34-35° 122-123°	(Diels & Alder, <i>loc. cit.</i>) (Diels & Alder, <i>loc. cit.</i>).
M.p. of the dicarboxylic acid	112-114°	111.5-113.5°	(Arbusow & Abramow, <i>Ber.</i> 1934, 67, 1942).

Fraction (II) from the result of analysis and molecular weight determination seemed to be a hydrocarbon of the composition $C_{20}H_{32}$. Its formation from myrcene on keeping and to some extent on distillation suggests that it is possibly dimyrcene. This has been proved to be correct. In chloroform solution it absorbs bromine and with nitrogen trioxide forms a nitrosite which melts with decomposition at 160°. Its various properties are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

Properties.	The compound.	Dimyrcene.	References.
B.p.	176°-178°/5.5 mm.	183°-184°/10 mm.	(Lebedev, <i>J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1913, 45, 1249, 1395).
Density	0.9041 at 30°	0.8763 at 20°	(Lebedev, <i>loc. cit.</i>)
n_D	1.5010 at 30°	1.49859 at 20°	(Lebedev, <i>loc. cit.</i>)
$[\alpha]_D$	0°	0°	
M.R.	88.63	$C_{20}H_{32}$ 3, 86.61	
M.p. of nitrosite	160° with decomposition	163° with decomposition	(Harrjes, <i>Ber.</i> , 1902, 35, 3254)

The behaviour of the diterpene from the resin is exactly like that of dimyrcene from para rubber described by Harries (*loc. cit.*). He mentions that after distilling the diterpene a residue is left which he calls polymyrcene and which with nitrogen trioxide in benzene solution gives a nitrosite melting with decomposition at 163°. We also obtained a similar residue after distilling off the diterpene and this gave with nitrogen trioxide in benzene solution a nitrosite which melted with decomposition at 163°. It will thus be seen that the characteristics and constituents of the essential oils from *C. mukul* and *C. myrrah* bear little resemblance to each other.

EXPERIMENTAL

Isolation of the Essential Oil.—The essential oil was obtained by steam-distillation of the resin (5 kilos) from a copper still fitted with a spiral copper condenser. The oil (12.5 c.c.) floating over the aqueous distillate was collected and from the aqueous layer 9.5 c.c. more were obtained by extraction with CCl_4 . The total yield of the oil (12.5 + 9.5 = 22 c.c.) was thus 0.37% of the weight of the resin.

Fractionation of the Oil.—The oil (36 c.c.) was fractionally distilled and the following fractions were obtained :

No.	B.p.	Vol.	Yield.
I.	106°-109°/120 mm. or 168°-170°/750 mm. Between 90°-176°/5.5 mm. (I and II)	23.1 c.c.	64%
II.	175°-177°/5.5 mm.	4	11
Residue	Above 178°/5.5 mm.	1.4	5

Isolation of Pure Myrcene from Fraction (I).—Preliminary analysis showed that this fraction was a hydrocarbon mixed with a small percentage of an oxygen containing compound. Hence it was distilled over sodium under reduced pressure and once more distilled at ordinary pressure. It was then analysed. [Found: C, 87.9; H, 11.6; M.W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 142; M.R., 46.85. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}$ requires C, 88.2; H, 11.8 per cent. M. W. 136; M.R./3, 46.66].

The Maleic Anhydride Adduct.—The pure terpene (2.6 c.c.) from fraction (I) was dissolved in dry benzene (6 c.c.) and the solution gradually added to a suspension of maleic anhydride (1.9 g.) in 5 c.c. of benzene. The reaction started within five minutes and the temperature rose from 16° to 33°. The mixture was allowed to remain at the room temperature for half an hour and then heated in a well-corked bottle (to exclude moisture) in a water-bath for 4 hours. The residue left on removal of the solvent was cooled in ice when a white solid separated, m.p. 33-34°, yield 3 g.

The Acid Potassium Salt.—The crude maleic anhydride adduct was hydrolysed with theoretical proportion of 30% KOH solution. Within 5 minutes of warming the mixture on a water-bath a sparingly soluble potassium salt of the corresponding dibasic acid separated. This was filtered and washed with ether to free it from unreacted terpene. It was then decomposed with 10% sulphuric acid when a thick

yellow oil separated which solidified on standing. The solid acid was filtered, washed with water and dried. It melted at 106° - 114° , but could not be obtained in definite crystalline form from usual organic solvents; although by repeated crystallisations from ethyl acetate the melting range could be narrowed to 110° - 114° . Arbusow and Abramow (*loc. cit.*) used methyl cyanide to crystallise this acid, but even then they could not get it in a sharply melting range. The acid was therefore converted into its acid potassium salt by warming it with molecular proportion of 30% caustic potash. On keeping the solution, so obtained, overnight, the acid potassium salt separated in fine white crystals, m.p. 150 - 51° . (Found: Equiv., 288.1. $C_{14}H_{10}O_4K$ requires equiv., 290).

Dimyrcene from Fraction (II).—Fraction (II) even on further distillation boiled at 176° - $178^{\circ}/5.5$ mm. It was then analysed. [Found: C, 88.0; H, 11.5; M.W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 259; M.R., 88.63. $C_{20}H_{12}$ requires C, 88.2; H, 11.8 per cent. M.W., 272; M.R. $\frac{1}{3}$, 88.61].

The Dimyrcene Nitrosite.—Fraction (II) (2 c.c.) was dissolved in 10 c.c. of dry benzene and through this well cooled solution a stream of nitrogen trioxide (generated from arsenious oxide and strong nitric acid) was passed till saturation. A gummy product separated which on drying hardened and could be powdered. It was then dissolved in minimum quantity of ethyl acetate and reprecipitated with absolute ether. The pure nitrosite melts at 160° with decomposition. [Found: N, 14.0. $(C_{10}H_{13}N_3O)_2$ (Harries, *loc. cit.*) requires N, 14.5 per cent].

The nitrosite of the polymyrcene was obtained similarly from the residue from the distillation of the oil. It melts with decomposition at 160° .

C O N C L U S I O N

The medicinal properties of myrcene or of its polymerides are not found on record and as these form the chief components of the essential oil from the resin it is not possible to say at this stage whether the medicinal properties of Gugal are on account of its volatile components. Probably these properties reside in the non-volatile part.

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